

NCC's Role in Nurturing Youth Dreams for Viksit Bharat: A Study

Dr. Dilip Kumar Sonowal¹ & Balo Ram Nath²

ABSTRACT

Viksit Bharat aims to transform India into a developed nation by 2047, marking 100 years of independence. The National Cadet Corps (NCC), established on July 15, 1948, supports youth goals with *Viksit Bharat@2047* through leadership, discipline, and national duty. As the largest uniformed youth organization in the world, NCC promotes patriotism through training and camps, helping develop personal qualities essential for growth and national progress. The study shows that NCC significantly influences youth aspirations. Most respondents, regardless of gender or academic stream of study (arts, science, commerce, BCA, B.Voc), agreed that training changed traditional mindsets towards comprehensive development. Benefits include leadership, life skills, adventure, resilience, social service, discipline, and women's empowerment. Differences in responses were due to misunderstandings of questions, rather than different perceptions. The study suggests increasing awareness efforts among cadets compared to other regions.

KEY WORDS: *Viksit Bharat, NCC, youth empowerment, leadership development, and national progress.*

1. Introduction:

Viksit Bharat represents the Government's goal to transform India into a developed nation by 2047, which marks 100 years of India's independence. To achieve this, it focuses on economic growth, social empowerment, infrastructure development, environmental sustainability, and inclusive governance. It promotes youth involvement, aims for zero poverty, increases women's participation, and strengthens farmers' roles in global food markets. In this context, the National Cadet Corps (NCC), founded on July 15, 1948, under the NCC Act XXXI of 1948 (Ministry of Defence, Government of India), plays a key role in connecting youth aspirations with *Viksit Bharat@2047* through leadership, discipline, and national duty. Recognized as the world's largest uniformed youth organization with over 2 million cadets, the NCC encourages patriotism through structured training and camps. This hands-on learning helps cadets develop

¹ Associate Professor, Department of Political Science & Associate NCC Officer, Kaliabor College

² Assistant Professor, Department of Political Science & Associate NCC Officer, Raha College

their personal qualities, contributing to their growth and the nation's progress. This paper examines NCC's role in supporting youth dreams for Viksit Bharat.

2. Objectives of the study:

- ❖ To evaluate NCC programs that build youth skills, discipline, and leadership in line with Viksit Bharat.
- ❖ To examine NCC's influence on youth dreams, ambitions, and their roles in Viksit Bharat's self-reliance and innovation.

3. Research Methodology and focus:

This study uses descriptive and analytical methods. Primary data is collected from surveys by adopting purposive random sampling of 130 NCC cadets (85 boys, 45 girls) in Nagaon district. The researcher also considered students' streams—Arts, Science, Commerce, and Professional courses—when selecting the sample for the study. Secondary data sources include ANO & Cadets' Handbooks, printed and online research papers, journals, books, and NCC official websites. Empirical observations from the researcher support the conclusions.

4. National Cadet Corps (NCC): A Brief Overview

NCC is the single largest uniformed youth organization in India which functions to develop qualities of character, leadership, comradeship, courage, discipline, spirit of adventure, secular outlook and the ideas of selfless service amid the youth of the country. National Cadet Corps is the tri-services organization, comprising the Army, Navy and Air Force, engaged in grooming the youth of the country into disciplined and patriotic citizens. It is the largest youth volunteers structured organization under the Ministry of Defence which enrol the students from High Schools, Colleges and Universities all over India.

4.1 The Growth and evolution of NCC in the context of International and Indian platform:

The history of NCC can be discussed broadly into two categories i.e.- International context and the Indian Context.

4.1.1 Growth and evolution of NCC in International platform:

Indian National Cadet Corps conceptual roots traced back to the German University Corps started in 1666 for youth military training. The purpose of German cadet Corps, historically was to train future military Officers and state servants, instilling discipline, loyalty, and skill for defence, evolving from Prussian royal needs to a tool for national ideology, especially under the Nazis (like Hitler Youth Corps) for militarization and indoctrination, focusing on obedience, strengths, and state service, while post WWII, the modern Bundeswehr (German Armed Forces) emphasizes loyalty to democratic values, through actual cadet training (like UOTC) bridges civilian life to military service, fostering leadership, teamwork and civic duty, distinct from the totalitarian aims of the past. The following heads are the most important phenomenon in the context of growth and evolutions of the NCC in German –

4.1.2. Early Prussian Cadets Schools (17th -18th Century)

Origins:

The concept of structured cadet training in Germany began with figures like the “Great Elector” Frederick William I, who established early corps in Kelberg, Berlin, and Magdeburge, with the Kolberg corps moving to Berlin in 1716 to form the core of the Royal Prussian Cadet Corps.

Expansions:

Under Frederick William I, known as the “Soldier King”, these schools became vital for Officer education, with further establishment in stolp, kulm, Postdam, and Kalisch.

4.2 Growth and evolution of NCC in Indian Context:

The National Cadet Corps (NCC) in India originated from the British era University Training Corps (UTC) and was officially formed on July 15, 1948 (NCC Act XXXI), under the National Cadet, it started with just twenty thousand cadets and quickly expanded to Army, Navy and Air Force Wings becoming a vital, voluntary tri – services organization grooming India’s youth for selfless service and nation- building, with the motto “Unity and Discipline”. Through the organization of National Cadet Corps (NCC) started in 1948, but it has a colourful history. It can be traced back to the ‘University Corps, which was created under the Indian Defence Act 1917, with an objective to make up for a shortage of personnel in the Army. In 1920, when the Indian Territorial Act was passed, the University Corps was replaced by the University Training Corps (UTC). The aim was to raise the status of the UTC and make it more attractive to the youth. UTC

Officers and cadets wear Army uniform. It was significant step towards the ‘Indianisation’ of the Indian Armed Forces. It was renamed of UOTC so the National Cadet Corps can be considered a successor to the University Officers Training Corps (UOTC) which was established by the Government of India in 1942. During the World war II, the UOTC never came up to the expectation set by the British. This led to the idea that some better schemes should be formed, which could train more young men in a better way, even during peace. The first Prime Minister of India, Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru presided over the function of raising the first NCC unit at Delhi on the fourth Sunday of November in 1982. This day is traditionally celebrated as the NCC day. A committee headed by H.N. Kunzru recommended a cadet organization to be established in schools and universities at a national level.

In 1949, the Girls Division was formed in order to provide equal opportunities to school and college going girls. The NCC was given an inter service image in 1950 when the Air Wing was added, followed by the Naval Wing in 1952. In the same year, the NCC Curriculum was extended to include community development/Social Service activities as a part of the NCC syllabus.

5. NCC: Organization and Structure

The National Cadet Corps (NCC) has a unique organisational structure that covers India. Fig. 1 shows the overall hierarchy, led by the Director General (DG), who is a Lieutenant General, at NCC Headquarters in New Delhi. Fig. 2 illustrates how NCC units are spread across educational institutions nationwide. This highlights their wide network for cadet training and development.

Fig.1 Organisational structure and division

Fig.2 NCC division in educational institutions

Source: NCC Cadets Hand Book

6. NCC Training Activities:

The NCC mainly provides **Institutional** and **Camp training** to cadets.

Fig.3 Training Activities of NCC

Source: NCC Cadets Hand Book

6.1 Institutional Training: Regular drills and parades take place in schools and colleges. This helps build discipline, punctuality, time management, and teamwork among cadets. This training forms the basis for their overall growth and prepares them for camp-based training and leadership positions (**fig.4**).

Fig.4 Institutional Training of NCC

Source: NCC Cadets Hand Book

6.2 Camp Training: Camps lasting 10 to 12 days aim to give cadets a regimental lifestyle while developing leadership skills and teamwork (**fig.5**)

Fig.5 Camp Training of NCC

Source: NCC Cadets Hand Book

7. Empowering Youth through NCC for Viksit Bharat Vision:

7.1 Leadership Development:

Table 1: Respondents' views on the importance of NCC training for youth.

Sex		Stream			
Male	Female	Arts	Science	Commerce	Professionals
80	36	103	6	4	3
(94.11%)	(80%)	(91.96)	(85.71)	(50)	(100)

Source: Field Survey

The study shows that the most respondents, including both males and females from streams like Arts, Science, Commerce, and professional courses, understand the importance of NCC training for youth today. This training helps develop leadership skills in cadets and builds discipline from an early age [Table 1]. It

also promotes a strong sense of patriotism, encouraging cadets to serve the nation selflessly. On the other hand, a few respondents noted improvements in physical fitness, academic learning, and sports abilities.

7.2 Personality and Life Skills:

Table 2: Respondents' views on NCC's role in developing personality.

Sex		Stream			
Male	Female	Arts	Science	Commerce	Professionals
27	59	75	6	3	3
(60%)	(69.41%)	(66.96)	(85.71)	(37.5%)	(100%)

Source: Field Survey

Table: 2 shows that most respondents recognize the important role of the NCC in shaping a cadet's personality. Among male respondents, 60% and among female respondents, 69% said that the NCC helps in develop qualities like discipline, empathy, humility, and creativity. These are all essential traits for a good personality. However, 33.33% of male respondents and 22.35% of female respondents believe that NCC training initially instills discipline in cadets. A similar pattern appeared among the respondents based on their fields of study. Specifically, 25.89% of arts students, 14.28% of science students, and 50% of all respondents highlighted discipline as key for developing personality.

Table 3: Respondents' views on NCC's role in cultivating life skills.

Sex		Stream			
Male	Female	Arts	Science	Commerce	Professionals
41	75	99	7	6	3
(91.11%)	(88.23%)	(88.39)	(100%)	(75%)	(100%)

Source: Field Survey

The study clearly shows NCC training's role in developing life skills. As shown in Table 3, most respondents agreed that it builds confidence, perseverance, and adaptability, which are essential for cadets' daily lives.

Only a few respondents, 6.66% of males and 8.23% of females, specifically mentioned academic skills development from NCC training. By stream, 7.14% of arts respondents and 25% of commerce respondents highlighted NCC's contribution to academic skills.

7.3 Adventure and Resilience Training:

Table 4: Respondents' views on NCC's role in decision-making and problem-solving skills.

Sex		Stream			
Male	Female	Arts	Science	Commerce	Professionals
34	69	90	5	6	2
(75.55%)	(81.17%)	(80.35%)	(71.42%)	(75%)	(66.66%)

Source: Field Survey

NCC training gives cadets the adventurous spirit to tackle tough situations at any time. A specific unit is included in the common subject curriculum for cadets. Table 4 shows NCC's important role in building decision-making and problem-solving skills. Most respondents said that NCC training puts cadets in challenging situations, which helps develop critical thinking and teamwork. However, less than 10% of respondents saw the training as focused only on routine tasks.

Table 5: Respondents' views on NCC's role in resilience training.

Sex		Stream			
Male	Female	Arts	Science	Commerce	Professionals
37	70	91	7	6	3
(82.22%)	(82.35%)	(81.25%)	(100%)	(75%)	(100%)

Source: Field Survey

The NCC training focuses on resilience training for cadets, which includes both psychological and physical parts. Over 82% of male and female respondents(table-5) said that this training helps them to manage stress, develop cognitive skills, regulate emotions, prioritize self-care, and build strong connections with others. Team-building exercises and group discussions improve communication and conflict resolution skills. In contrast, less than 11% of respondents mentioned the physical aspects only.

7.4 Social Service and Community Development:

Table 6: Respondents' views on NCC's role in SSCD activities.

Sex		Stream			
Male	Female	Arts	Science	Commerce	Professionals
41	81	106	6	7	3
(91.11%)	(95.29%)	(94.64%)	(85.71%)	(87.5%)	(100%)

Source: Field Survey

Table 6 shows that more than 85% of respondents, across gender and academic streams, supported an active role in continuing social service and community development activities in their local areas. They stressed that community service and social responsibility start with raising awareness and include sharing government populist policies with the public. This aligns with national goals like Viksit Bharat@2047. In this context, they also supported encouraging individual achievements along with social involvement.

7.5 Discipline and National Integration:

Table 7: Respondents' Views on NCC's role in maintaining Discipline

Sex		Stream			
Male	Female	Arts	Science	Commerce	Professionals
43	82	110	6	7	2
(95.55%)	(96.47%)	(98.21%)	(85.71%)	(87.5%)	(66.66%)

Source: Field Survey

Table 7 shows the important role of NCC in building discipline among cadets. Respondents are familiar with NCC's motto: "Unity and Discipline." The study indicates that NCC training fosters punctuality, responsibility, cooperation, and mutual respect, which are the building blocks of discipline. It also improves cadets' physical strength and endurance while promoting healthy individual competition.

Table 8: Respondents' Views on NCC's Role in Promoting National Integration

Sex		Stream			
Male	Female	Arts	Science	Commerce	Professionals
36	73	95	7	7	3
(80%)	(85.88%)	(84.82%)	(100%)	(87.5%)	(100%)

Source: Field Survey

The NCC syllabus includes a unit on National Integration as a common subject. This shows the NCC's efforts to promote National Integration. 80% of male respondents and 85.88% of female respondents (table:8) believe that by encouraging equal participation, respecting diversity, and fostering teamwork, the NCC works to ensure inclusivity, fairness, and mutual respect among cadets from different backgrounds. Additionally, the National Integration Camp and Ek Bharat Shreshtha Bharat (EBSB) Camp are important NCC initiatives launched by the Government of India to promote national integration and unity in diversity.

7.6 Women empowerment:

Table 9: Respondents' Views on NCC's Role in Women's Empowerment.

Sex		Stream			
Male	Female	Arts	Science	Commerce	Professionals
41	81	106	6	7	3
(91.11%)	(95.29%)	(94.64%)	(85.71%)	(87.5%)	(100%)

Source: Field Survey

Table 9 shows that most respondents recognize NCC's active role in empowering women. They acknowledge many awareness campaigns on anti-dowry and gender equality, skill-building programs like entrepreneurship and self-defense, and cultural initiatives that create a supportive environment and challenge stereotypes about women. NCC has increased female participation by raising enrollment of girl cadets, organizing special drives, and setting quotas across the Army, Navy, and Air Wings. To develop leadership skills, girl cadets take part in Republic Day Camp (RDC) and Thal Sainik Camp. Seminars and workshops are also held to focus on safety, overall well-being, and leadership for girl cadets.

8. Conclusion:

The study shows that the NCC has significantly influenced youth aspirations for Viksit Bharat. Most respondents, regardless of gender or academic field, agreed that structured training in institutions and camps changed their traditional views. This shift helped them focus on personal growth and national development for Viksit Bharat. Respondents noted improvements in leadership skills, personality and life skills, adventure and resilience training, social service and community involvement, discipline and national unity, and the empowerment of women. Variations in responses among males, females, and different academic fields (arts, science, commerce, BCA, B.Voc) were mainly due to misunderstandings of the questions, not differences in perceptions. The study suggests increasing awareness initiatives among cadets in comparison to other regions.

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